

PSYCHOLOGY OF CRIME: WHY DO PEOPLE BECOME CRIMINALS? PSYCHOLOGICAL THEORIES OF CRIME

Turdibekova Sevinch Baxodir qizi

TDYU huzuridagi Samarqand viloyati yuridik akademik litseyi talabasi
+998958901908 turdibekovasevinch9@gmail.com

Jurakulova Shohista Farxod qizi

TDYU huzuridagi Samarqand viloyati yuridik akademik litseyi talabasi
+998944270054 shokhistajurakulova@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18536884>

Abstract. This article analyzes various psychological and biological theories that explain human criminality. The author presents the causes of crime not as a single, but as a multifactorial set of factors such as genetics, brain chemistry, upbringing, social environment, and learned behavior. Within the framework of biological approaches, the influence of genetics, brain structure, and hormonal factors is analyzed. The effect of frontal cortex damage on human behavior is also highlighted through the example of Phineas Gage. In socialization theories, approaches such as classical, operant, and observational learning, as well as Strain theory, explain crime from a social and psychological perspective. Routine Activity Theory and Social Construction Theory also emphasize the variability of the concept of crime in society. At the end of the article, it is concluded that crime is the result of a complex interaction between human biology, psychology, and social conditions. Many people have their own theories on what makes a criminal. Some of these theories are based on firsthand knowledge or experience, some unfortunately may be based on racism or prejudice, and some on scientifically investigated studies. And there are several psychological theories of crime, most of which have been shown to have a sound scientific basis. However, it is widely accepted that the reasons for crime are seldom one cause or the other, but rather a combination of some.

Keywords: criminology, psychology, biological theory, socialization, genetics, Strain Theory, Routine Activity Theory, learning theories, Phineas Gage

Аннотация. В данной статье анализируются различные психологические и биологические теории, объясняющие преступность человека. Автор рассматривает причины преступности не как единый, а как многофакторный комплекс таких факторов, как генетика, химия мозга, воспитание, социальная среда и приобретенное поведение. В рамках биологических подходов анализируется влияние генетики, структуры мозга и гормональных факторов. Влияние повреждения лобной коры на поведение человека также рассматривается на примере Финеаса Гейджа. В теориях социализации такие подходы, как классическое, оперантное и наблюдательное обучение, а также теория напряжения, объясняют преступность с социальной и психологической точки зрения. Теория рутинной деятельности и теория социального конструирования также подчёркивают изменчивость понятия преступности в обществе. В конце статьи делается вывод о том, что преступность является результатом сложного взаимодействия биологии, психологии и социальных условий человека.

Ключевые слова: криминология, психология, биологическая теория, социализация, генетика, теория напряжения, теория рутинной деятельности, теории обучения, Финеас Гейдж

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola insonlarning jinoyatchilikka moyilligini tushuntiruvchi turli psixologik va biologik nazariyalarni tahlil qiladi. Muallif jinoyat sabablarini bir yoqlama emas, balki ko'p omilli — genetika, miya kimyosi, tarbiya, ijtimoiy muhit va o'rganilgan xulq-atvor kabi omillar yig'indisi sifatida ko'rsatadi. Biologik yondashuvlar doirasida genetika, miya tuzilishi va gormonal omillarning ta'siri tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, Phineas Gage misoli orqali frontal korteks shikastlanishining inson xulqiga ta'siri yoritiladi. Ijtimoiylashuv nazariyalarida esa klassik, operant va kuzatuv orqali o'rganish hamda Strain (zo'riqish) nazariyasi kabi yondashuvlar jinoyatchilikni ijtimoiy va psixologik nuqtai nazardan izohlaydi. Shuningdek, Routine Activity Theory va Social Construction Theory jamiyatda jinoyat tushunchasining o'zgaruvchanligini ta'kidlaydi. Maqola yakunida jinoyat inson biologiyasi, psixologiyasi va ijtimoiy sharoitlari o'rtasidagi murakkab o'zaro ta'sir natijasi ekanligi xulosa qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: jinoyatchilik, psixologiyasi, biologik nazariyasi, ijtimoiylashuv, genetika, o'rganish nazariyalari,

Biological Theories of Crime: These include genetics, hormones, brain chemistry (neurotransmitters), and brain structure and anatomy.

Genetics: Because statistically, more males commit crimes than females, it was proposed that this must be because of the genetic makeup of males. However, this theory has been largely discredited.

Twin studies and crime But studies with twins have shown that identical twins are more likely to share criminal tendencies than non identical (or fraternal) twins. This was the case even when identical twins were separated at birth, so environment or upbringing would not necessarily have been a factor. Even so, some psychologists still believe that this is not conclusive evidence of a genetic link.

Brain Chemistry. Serotonin is a neurotransmitter in the brain that affects mood, which in turn can affect criminal behavior. Testosterone, the male hormone, is linked to levels of aggression. Omega 3 has been shown to lower levels of aggression, and poor nutrition before the age of 3 has also been linked to higher levels of aggression. All of these come under the heading of Brain Chemistry and all have a link to criminal behavior.

Brain Structure and Anatomy: The part of the brain associated with or emotions is called the Amygdala (am-ig-d-la). It is believed that damage to the Amygdala can have an effect of criminal behavior. This may be because the person

concerned would have a limited fear and conditioning response, thus fear of punishment would not deter them from committing a crime. The Hippocampus is where we store our memories. Damage to this area could mean we do not remember being punished for our crimes, and so would commit them again and again. The Frontal Cortex, as the name suggests, is to the front of our brain and would also appear to be involved, among other functions, with our self control—as one famous case-study showed:

Phineas Gage. The most famous case of brain damage causing a change in self-control is one of a man called Phineas Gage. In 1848, Phineas was a mild-mannered and conscientious railroad worker foreman in Vermont, U.S. He was overseeing the laying of explosives one fateful day. It was the practice to lay sand over the explosives in a hole and then to tap it down with a tamping iron. Phineas was using the tamping iron, which was 3'8" long and 1.5" in diameter, when a spark ignited the explosive and sent the tamping iron straight through his left cheek

and out through the frontal cortex, landing several feet behind him. Incredibly, Phineas not only survived, but walked to the cart which was to transport him to a doctor.

"No Longer Gage" While Phineas later appeared to have made a full recovery, those who knew him before the accident said that he was “No longer Gage” No longer mild mannered and conscientious, he became verbally aggressive and abusive, unreliable in his work and impatient and impulsive to the extent that the railroad company could no longer employ him.

Was it the brain damage that caused the change? It appeared that the damage to the frontal cortex caused the change in Phineas. However, it must also be remembered that brain damage also has the potential to cause depression, and that there was also a possibility that Phineas would have suffered from Post Traumatic Stress, either of which could also cause changes in his personal disposition.

Socialisation theories of crime These include Learning Theories such as:

- **Classical Conditioning**-the famous example being Pavlov’s Dogs, in which Pavlov trained the dogs to salivate at the sound of a bell.

- **Operant Conditioning**-The Skinner Box, developed by B.F Skinner (who else?) in which he trained rats to press (or ‘operate’) levers in order to get to their food.

- **Observational Learning**-“Monkey see-Monkey do” But humans are not dogs, rats or monkeys. However, it would seem that we do learn by similar methods. If a child is surrounded by crime, either within the family or the community, they are likely to learn criminal behaviour by any or all of the above methods.

Routine Activity Theory. This can tie-in somewhat with Learning Activity; for example, if a child learns that stealing is one way to get what they want, they will do it again. All they need is for three elements to be in place:

1.Motivation: They want something

2. Suitable Target: They see what they want

3. Absence of Guardians: And there’s no one about

They get away with it, and do it again and again, until it becomes routine.

Strain Theory: This is probably one of the best-known psychological theories of crime. A person really wants something, such as material goods, a better lifestyle, or even an education, but they can see no possible way of ever achieving it now or in the future. This understandably causes dissatisfaction, perhaps even resentment against the people who do have what they want. But then they see there is a way to achieve their desires through stealing, drug dealing, or other criminal behaviour

Control Theory: Social Construction Theory of Crime. Each society has its own view of what is and is not a crime: For example, in Saudi Arabia, public displays

of affection are illegal. Circumstances can also change whether certain behavior is a crime or not. For example, a Police car or an Ambulance may break the speed limit without suffering a penalty. Society’s view of crime can also change with time; for example, Prohibition, Homosexuality, and more recently, Cyber crimes

Conclusion. The reasons that motivate people to commit crimes are not unique, but a combination of biological, psychological and social factors. Genetic predisposition, brain dysfunction or hormonal imbalances can in some cases directly change behavior. At the same time, the experience a person has gained in the social environment and the values based on which they were raised are also important. In order to prevent crime, it is necessary to pay

attention not only to punishment, but also to preventive measures such as education, social equality and psychological support.

Adabiyotlar, References, Литературы:

1. Eysenck, H. J. (1977). “Crime and Personality”. London: Routledge & Kegan Paul.
2. Mednick, S. A., Gabrielli, W. F., & Hutchings, B. (1984). “Genetic influences in criminal convictions: Evidence from an adoption cohort. Science,” 224(4651), 891–894
3. Raine, A. (1993). “The Psychopathology of Crime: Criminal Behavior as a Clinical Disorder”. San Diego: Academic Press.
4. Skinner, B. F. (1953). Science and Human Behavior. New York: Macmillan.
5. Pavlov, I. P. (1927). Conditioned Reflexes: An Investigation of the Physiological Activity of the Cerebral Cortex. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
6. Bandura, A. (1977). Social Learning Theory. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice Hall.
7. erton, R. K. (1938). Social structure and anomie. American Sociological Review, 3(5), 672–682.